

THE INFLUENCE OF FINE ART IN INCREASE STUDENTS' ARTISTIC THINKING AND CREATIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract: The article contains information about the effect of fine art on increasing the artistic thinking and creative activity of students, the artistic creativity and creative process in fine art, and the aesthetic pleasure of people by reading, seeing, and hearing works of art.

Key words: student, creativity, thinking, Goya, visual arts, artistic creativity, aesthetic taste, art

As we know, artistic ideas are the main meaning and content of fine art. Artistic ideas are taken from life and affect the human mind and psyche based on artistic expressions. This increases people's positive behavior, initiative, artistic-aesthetic taste, and culture, and ensures their aspiration towards a specific goal. In visual arts, man creates his own ideas. The mind and consciousness, thinking, and faith of a person who enjoys the ideas created by himself and gets strength - power rises. High ideals lead a person to noble goals. Creative ideas that make the country prosperous and people's life prosperous include noble goals. Also, the struggle to eliminate alien ideas in the human mind and heart is the main direction of this process.

The inspiring power of fine art, its place and importance in society is that any artistic-aesthetic activity encourages a person to social action and activity. This, in turn, increases the strong confidence in the great future of our country. As a result, in the heart of every citizen, love for the homeland, Uzbekistan, work in the spirit of loyalty to the idea of independence, the desire to increase the cultural, artistic-aesthetic potential of their homeland, and learn the art and culture of their people and embody the beautiful feelings that permeate the human heart and mind.

The influence of fine art is so strong that people absorb any progressive idea, understand that a person can be free only if the Motherland is free, and can respond against any evil idea, and most importantly, people's independent worldview and free thinking are formed, they realize their national identity, it will be possible to educate national pride and pride. In particular, the creative qualities characteristic of our national nature, the sense of respect and patriotism for the holy land of our fathers and grandfathers, and the concept of beauty will expand. In this regard, it is appropriate to think about creativity in creativity and artistic activity.

Creativity is a higher level of consciousness and a complex form of activity, which is characteristic of a person. Creativity is a miracle born as a result of human knowledge, skills, competence, experience and skills. Creativity and creative processes in art, especially in visual arts, the result of creativity is the creation of a work of art. Artistic creativity in visual arts is realized through the creative process. In this, the creator creates a work of art by

summarizing the ideological artistic content. In this, the artist's work, will, feelings, memory, thinking, intuition and imagination are manifested as spiritual and practical abilities.

Thus, the will activates creativity as a great force. As a result, a person achieves high results and is formed as a person. With the participation of artistic thinking, existence can be deeply and comprehensively understood. In fact, a work of art is a product of thought. Thinking includes the ideological-aesthetic content of the work of art, as well as worldview and philosophical understanding. Imagination is involved in artistic creation. Creative imagination plays an important role in creative activity.

Inspiration in visual activity ensures quality work with great interest and joy. Intuition-sensitivity is important in human mental activity, i.e. in creative work, especially in artistic creation, which opens a wide path to continuous work and finding new solutions under its influence. A positive effect and consequence of the concept of genius, which is considered a superior quality of ability and talent in artistic creation, is that it leads to the creation of works of art of worldly importance.

The word art means to make, to work, to polish. Artistically and aesthetically reflecting the reality of life in visual activity, warning people from evil and darkness, and educating them on the basis of high ideals serve goodness. Most importantly, literature and art in any form promote humanity.

The way of life of young people, their way of life, their politeness, their devotion to work and profession are in accordance with the standards of moral education of the national culture. This is connected with the formation of a new worldview in young people, education in the national spirit, development of noble feelings, and achievement of spiritual perfection. In the process of spiritual growth of young people, their legal, political, moral, cultural and ideological ideas are formed and developed. By forming creativity in students, we mean not the creation of some kind of object or artistic work, but the ability to approach each task from its own point of view, to be able to think independently on a problem, to be able to connect all the knowledge acquired during the study to events in life and analyze them, in the field of study we must understand that he expresses his new views. It is necessary to pay special attention to the development of students' ability to express their thoughts in writing.

Fine art is the oldest, and it is divided into such types as sculpture, painting, graphics. It has portrait, landscape, still life, historical, military, animal, household genres. Fine art is an art in which reality, existence is depicted by the artist on a certain plane, surface, space, etc., through the application of shapes, lines, colors, paints. Fine art is a special form of social consciousness, which helps people to learn about the world, to consciously understand the complex and important aspects of life. It shows and visualizes a vivid image of reality. Fine art gives a person aesthetic pleasure. It provides a sense of beauty in a person, higher human feelings, ideological confidence, spiritual independence, and courage. The direct task of fine art in educating the people from an artistic-aesthetic point of view is to create works of art that are suitable for our time and stand at the level of its great ideas and achievements.

The most important task for artists is to bridge the gap between art, life, work and beauty. For example, beauty is not pure, it always appears in connection with something. Straight figure, clear eyes, straight teeth are beauty, all these indicate health, activity, strength and enthusiasm of a person. In this respect, the demand for an artist's work is also reflected in the faithfulness to the reality of life. It should be emphasized that everyone should have aesthetic culture and ability to feel the beauty in visual arts. This in turn ensures that one's

desire to create beauty is active and creative, and creates the basis for enjoying beauty and bringing it to life.

The most beautiful product of nature is also the stage of its development - a person who has the same mind - intelligence, will, and the ability to create. It is worth noting that visual art has a very strong positive effect on people's minds, and its main task is to educate a spiritually rich person who has matured in all aspects. Also, visual art is important in enjoying the historical, moral, cultural, and spiritual values of our nation, the wealth of world civilization. It reflects the lives of creative people and their creative power, trust, humanitarianism, loyalty, heroic courage, human image, our glorious history, bright pages of our current life, and their activities in the implementation of the national ideal. It also deeply and comprehensively illuminates the nature of ideas alien to the people.

As a result, by means of effective discussion, impartial criticism and analysis, the most important thing for the healing of the ideological environment in the world of creativity is to mature the members of our society, the young generation, to awaken in their hearts the national idea, national ideology, love and loyalty to their homeland, self-awareness, national and universal education in the spirit of values is achieved. By means of visual art, people can freely express their thoughts and ideas, their reaction to the happening events, increasing the political and spiritual activity of the population, and developing the artistic-aesthetic taste. Fine art is reflected in the artistic, practical and creative work aimed at changing people's social consciousness based on the laws of beauty, which allows to understand the spiritual world of a person, to get acquainted with its inner secrets. The main task of fine art is to reflect the human being, his multifaceted social activities, to satisfy his spiritual needs, and to develop his creative abilities.

The educational task of fine art is to deliver the rich cultural, artistic and aesthetic heritage created by mankind to future generations, it is a tool that satisfies people's needs, observes their feelings and emotions, changes the world based on the laws of beauty, and serves to form elegant feelings and emotions in people. Also, the most important activity of visual arts is to provide people with aesthetic pleasure and enjoyment by reading, seeing, and hearing works of art.

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